

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF MASTERING MUSIC- THEORETICAL KNOWLEDGE IN SPECIALIZED MUSIC SCHOOLS

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Annotation: This article discusses the pedagogical conditions for mastering musical-theoretical knowledge in specialized music schools, the differences in the process of mastering musical-theoretical knowledge in general secondary schools and specialized music schools in comparison.

Keywords: school, music, activity, comparison, country, theory, harmony, knowledge, upbringing, institution.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada ixtisoslashgan musiqa maktablarida musiqiy-nazariy bilimlarning o'zlashtirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari, umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari bilan ixtisoslashgan musiqa maktablarida musiqiy-nazariy bilimlarni o'zlashtirish jarayoni qiyoslashdagi farqlari haqida yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: maktab, musiqa, faoliyat, qiyoslash, mamlakat, nazariya, garmoniya, bilim, tarbiya, muassasa.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются педагогические условия усвоения музыкально-теоретических знаний в специальных музыкальных школах, а также различия в процессе усвоения музыкально-теоретических знаний в общеобразовательных средних школах и специальных музыкальных школах.

Ключевые слова: школа, музыка, деятельность, сравнение, страна, теория, гармония, знание, образование, учреждение.

The state program for the implementation of the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for the period of 2022-2026 in the "Year of honoring human dignity and active neighborhood" on additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art.[1] Pedagogical conditions for mastering musical-theoretical knowledge in specialized music schools Musical activity is an integral part of all our educational work, and its role in the harmonious development of young people is great. That is why at present in our country there are many music schools, many creative teams are being organized in school and out-of-school children's, cultural enlightenment institutions, and production organizations. Their main goal is to attract children to the art of music in large numbers, to love and appreciate it, and to cultivate their musical abilities. Music, with its unique nature, has the power to greatly influence the spiritual world of young people.[2] Considering that musical-theoretical

knowledge is fully provided only in specialized music schools, determining the forms and methods and techniques of providing musical-theoretical knowledge in these educational institutions will allow them to be used in general secondary educational institutions in the future.

To this end, targeted work was carried out to determine the scope of musical-theoretical knowledge in the curriculum and program of specialized music schools, to study the conditions created for mastering musical-theoretical knowledge, the methodological approaches used in the educational process, to compare the process of providing specialized musical knowledge with that of general secondary schools, and we got acquainted with the work of the “Music Theory” department of the primary music school of the Republican Specialized Academic Music Lyceum named after Glier and conducted observation work. Specialized music schools have departments of “Music Theory” and “Music History”, the “Music Theory” department includes subjects such as solfeggio, 196 music literacy, rhythmic, music theory, harmony, analysis of musical works, the “Music History” department includes subjects such as listening to music, musical literature, and Uzbek music. Each subject is taught by its own specialist. The classrooms are compact and comfortable, each room has tables and chairs, a piano, display posters, a blackboard for notes and text writing.

The classrooms are protected from outside noise. The school has a stock of gramophone records on music theory, and special literature necessary for students to master music theory. According to the curriculum, the number of students in the music theory department should not exceed ten, and the number of students in the music history department should not exceed twelve. According to the curriculum, in the primary school, students attend two hours of solfeggio, two hours of rhythm, and one hour of music listening lessons per week. This means that in the primary school, students are allocated a total of five hours to master music theory knowledge. This, in turn, increases the effectiveness of students' mastery of music theory knowledge. It is worth noting that specialized music schools satisfy the spiritual needs of students and fill in the gaps that arise during school education.

At the same time, individual work, differentiated teaching, the application of which in the process of school education is somewhat difficult, allows you to provide theoretical and practical knowledge that is not taken into account in the programs of the subject “Musical Culture”, integrates and enriches the educational mechanism. Specialized music schools differ from general secondary schools in the relatively large amount of knowledge that must be mastered. In

addition, it is necessary to check the octave of some frets in each string.[3] The process of mastering musical-theoretical knowledge in specialized music schools is carried out using the following methods and forms:

1) Educational methods that affect the minds of students - storytelling, explanation, highlighting, mnemonics, practical examples, demonstration, modeling, discussions;

2) Organization of creative activity - performing exercises, repeating and reinforcing, pedagogical requirements, giving assignments, using educational situations, etc;

3) Use of punishment and incentive methods in the educational process;

4) Application of the acquired theoretical knowledge in practice;

5) Organization of small musical dictations and control lessons. The principles that form the worldview of the choral culture are especially important today, when universal spiritual values are being revived.[4] The organization of educational work in specialized music schools to form the student's personality in the process of mastering musical and theoretical knowledge was carried out based on the following tools:

- personal approach and abilities of teachers and students;
- information and technical means;
- demonstration;
- visual aids;
- use of new technologies.

According to our observations, the process of mastering musical and theoretical knowledge in specialized music schools was carried out in accordance with the following principles:

1. Unity of musical education and upbringing.
2. The mastering of musical and theoretical knowledge is directed towards a single goal.
3. The relevance of musical knowledge to life.
4. Taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students.
5. Regular and systematic conduct of musical and theoretical classes. The teacher also examines each child's musical ability.[5]

Compared with general secondary schools, the following aspects of the process of mastering musical and theoretical knowledge in specialized music schools can be distinguished:

- 1) A lot of time is allocated per week for lessons;
- 2) A high level of interest in the lesson by students;

- 3) A much higher level of knowledge and qualifications of teachers (specialists who graduated from specialized higher educational institutions);
- 4) Each lesson is aimed at a specific goal;
- 5) The sufficiency of visual aids in classrooms and their effective use in lessons;
- 6) The use of new technologies in lessons;
- 7) Classes are divided into groups and the number of students in each group does not exceed ten. It is these factors that ensure the effectiveness of mastering musical-theoretical knowledge in special music schools. Music and singing activities have been of special importance in compositional creativity since ancient times.[6] It is also worth noting that the mastering of musical-theoretical knowledge in special music schools is supplemented with other special subjects. This allows you to consolidate the knowledge gained in lessons. The music theory course provides students with the necessary information about the art of music and the main means of musical expression that unites the “language” of music - melody.

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